

RADx-UP BRIEF

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

Investing in community engagement to achieve health equity

At the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, health inequities became more apparent when some underserved populations became more ill, tested less and were vaccinated less. Health researchers at **The National Institutes of Health (NIH)** hypothesized that to address health

inequities during the pandemic and beyond, the work must begin in partnership with communities. Beginning in April 2020, the NIH invested \$500M in 144 research projects across the country to test how to best keep communities most affected by COVID-19 safe. Successful RADx-UP community engagement approaches may be applied to other public health crises and community health practices to address health inequities in the U.S.

Community Engagement

An ongoing process of building and nurturing relationships of mutual understanding and trust between communities and those seeking to connect with them, including liaising between community partners and larger systems.

RADx-UP Projects

by specific populations engaged

September, 2023. Data is self-reported by projects. Projects may serve more than one population.

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT OUTCOMES

Community Engagement Scholarship Findings

In an analysis of 231 publications, 44 articles were coded under 'impacts of collaborative partnerships and community engagement.' Twenty-five of those articles describe how the following community engagement and collaborative partnership activities led to positive impacts in COVID-19 testing.

Accessing diverse partnerships to implement, adapt, and promote testing and vaccination

Strengthening recruitment and data collection

Improving community capacity for research and workforce development

Informing health messaging, outreach, and dissemination strategies

Utilizing community advisory boards (CABs) and community-based participatory research (CBPR) to guide research implementation

Building sustainable, trusted relationships within communities

Evaluating the impacts and strengths of community engagement

Policy Recommendations for Health Care Delivery Reform

In a review of 16 papers exploring the roles of **Community Health Workers (CHW)** in COVID-19 testing success, the RADx-UP team developed the policy brief "*Prioritizing Community*

Health Workers in Health Care Reform is Key to Enhancing Health Equity." The brief outlines how "lay health advisers" are essential links between community members and

health care services. The brief made recommendations to health policy investments in CHWs and payment models that support them.

SHORT-TERM

Revise federal quality measures

Expand payment models

Align CHW roles to reimbursement

LONG-TERM

Develop multi-year funding grants

Support CHWs in leadership

A FOUNDATION FOR ENGAGEMENT

The RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC)

created an infrastructure that supported community engagement work throughout the project lifecycle.

- The non-profit, **Community-Campus Partnerships for Health (CCPH)** helped guide community engagement work by participating in working groups and capacity-building webinars. Specifically, CCPH reviewed RADx-UP educational materials

for lay language and developed the “Racial Equity in the US Healthcare System Guidebook.”

- **Engagement Impact Teams (EITs)** were established to regularly meet with projects to understand challenges and create opportunities for successful project implementation.
- **Community Collaboration Grants** The CDCC Community Collaboration Grant program (C2G) awarded up to \$55,000 to 70 community organizations for a total investment of \$3,771,012 to help advance capacity, training, support, and community experience with COVID-19 testing initiatives for underserved populations. Community-serving organizations, faith-based organizations, and tribal nations and organizations could apply the grants to direct costs of testing programming.

Principles of Community Engagement

Early in its work, RADx-UP looked to evidence-based resources such as **The Principles of Community Engaged Research** (second edition) developed by federal agencies, and feedback from community partners, to better understand how community engaged research could better deliver COVID-19 testing to underserved populations.

From Principles of Community Engagement report, June 2011:

Community engagement can take many forms, and partners can include organized groups, agencies, institutions, or individuals. Collaborators may be engaged in health promotion, research, or policy making.

Community Health Framework

RADx-UP built a policy framework to describe its approach to mitigating health disparities in the U.S. It developed the “**Community-Based COVID-19 Testing: Barriers, Solutions and Next Steps.**” This policy paper outlines three learning areas:

- Common barriers that prevent fair access to COVID-19 testing
- Policy solutions to increase access to COVID-19 testing and other services
- Ideas to improve responses during COVID-19 or other public health emergencies

Documenting Community Feedback

The **Understanding Social Determinants of Testing and Vaccination Workgroup** documented feedback loops and dynamics within RADx-UP believed to be most important in shaping COVID testing in U.S. communities. The group focused on the critical role of social determinants of health that impact COVID-19 testing.

Confusion in changing recommendations and guidance

KEY

→ = a change in the starting variable triggers a change in the connected variable

S → = **same relationship** (as one goes up or down, so does the other)

O → = **opposite relationship** (i.e. as one goes up/down, the other does opposite)

R = **Reinforcing**; a feedback loop where changes are reinforced over time.

BUILDING TRUST

Community and academic partners repeatedly cited trust and long-term relationships as key to successful community engagement in research.

We have partnerships with the neighborhoods where we may have to dispatch and set up another pop-up testing site. We have those partnerships already built, and it won't take much to initiate them again if we need to."

—Community Partner, RADx-UP Testing and Evaluation qualitative report, a diverse sampling of 24 community and academic partners.

Our community advisory board (CAB) has been instrumental to helping us build trust in a highly research-reticent community, so much so that the members of the community felt comfortable sharing their honest and candid opinions in a research setting."

—Jalissa Shealey, RADx-UP project REPRESENT ATL: Increasing Representation of Black Communities in SARS-CoV-2 Serosurveys by Understanding Barriers and Motivations

Sharing Evidence

The annual **Evidence Academy (EA)** conference was designed to help RADx-UP projects strengthen their community-centered research aims and advance equity in COVID-19 testing and other public health initiatives.

The agenda highlighted speakers and sessions focused on building community-academic connections, enhancing knowledge of promising approaches, and lessons learned in engaging communities in COVID-19 testing and vaccines.

EA shared results through presentation videos, data profiles summarizing evidence, community/academic collaborations, and strategies for translating lessons learned.

Key takeaways from the COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy keynote address.

BUILDING RELATIONSHIPS

Study Design and Representation

The voices, lived experiences, and images of communities served were represented in all facets of RADx-UP work. Community partner inclusion during planning meetings, data collection and research results discussions were imperative to success.

The rapid launch of the study design in the early days of the pandemic, and specifically the adoption of standardized **NIH Common Data Elements (CDEs)**, proved an initial challenge to implement uniformly in every setting. In phase II, researchers were able to discuss community preferences to adapt CDEs to suit specific populations.

Whenever possible, community and academic partners collaborated on writing and presenting their research. RADx-UP developed more than a dozen **research briefs**, and its materials have been translated into **17 languages**. The **RADx-UP Image Bank** captured 1,222 project images from around the country to represent the work.

Communities of Practice

The CDCC coordinated and compensated members to serve on **Community Advisory Boards and Working Groups** in response to community-identified needs.

These groups brought together community members, researchers and content experts to provide guidance on the special considerations of underserved populations.

There have been eight RADx-UP Working Groups, including:

- Engaging Black/African Americans
- Community Health Workers
- Sexual and Gender Minorities
- Understanding Social Determinants of COVID-19
- Child Health
- Building Community Capacity and Impact
- SEBI: Social, Ethical and Behavioral Implications
- Engaging Hispanic/Latino/Latinx Populations

